

Published Global Crop Conservation Strategies

The list includes documents developed/or facilitated by several organizations. The strategies are listed in alphabetical order.

Crop	Year of publication	Strategy title
Apple	2019	A Global Strategy for the Conservation and Use of Apple Genetic Resources
Aroids	2010	Edible Aroid Conservation Strategies
Bananas	2006	Global Conservation Strategy for <i>Musa</i> (Banana and Plantain): A Consultative Document Prepared in Consultation with Partners in the <i>Musa</i> Research-and-Development Community
Bananas	2016	Global Strategy for the Conservation and Use of <i>Musa</i> (Banana) Genetic Resources
Barley	2008	Global Strategy for the <i>Ex situ</i> Conservation and Use of Barley Germplasm
Beans	2014	Conservation of <i>Phaseolus</i> Beans Genetic Resources: A Strategy
Brassica	2023	Global Strategy for the Conservation of <i>Brassica</i> Genetic Resources
Breadfruit	2007	Breadfruit Conservation Strategy
Cacao	2012	A Global Strategy for the Conservation and Use of Cacao Genetic Resources, as the Foundation for a Sustainable Cocoa Economy
Capsicum	2022	A Global Strategy for the Conservation and Use of <i>Capsicum</i> Genetic Resources
Cassava	2010	A Global Conservation Strategy for Cassava (<i>Manihot esculenta</i>) and Wild <i>Manihot</i> Species
Chickpea	2008	Global Strategy for the <i>Ex Situ</i> Conservation of Chickpea (<i>Cicer</i> L.)
Citrus	2023	A Global Strategy for the Conservation and Use of Citrus Genetic Resources (2023)
Coconut	2018	Global Conservation Strategy for the Conservation and Use of Coconut Genetic Resources
Coffee	2017	Global Conservation Strategy of Coffee Genetic Resources
Cowpea	2010	Global Strategy for the Conservation of Cowpea (<i>Vigna unguiculata</i> subsp. <i>unguiculata</i>)
Cucurbits	2021	A Global Conservation Strategy for Crops in the Cucurbitaceae Family
Eggplant	2022	Global Strategy for the Conservation and Use of Eggplants
Faba bean	2009	Global Strategy for the <i>Ex Situ</i> Conservation of Faba Bean (<i>Vicia faba</i> L.)
Finger millet	2012	Global Strategy for the <i>Ex Situ</i> Conservation of Finger Millet and its Wild Relatives
Forage (tropical and subtropical)	2015	A Global Strategy for the Conservation and Utilization of Tropical and Sub-Tropical Forage Genetic Resources
Forages (temperate)	2021	Global Strategy for the <i>Ex situ</i> Conservation of Temperate Forages
Grasspea	2007	Strategy for the <i>Ex Situ</i> Conservation of <i>Lathyrus</i> (Grass Pea), with Special Reference to <i>Lathyrus sativus</i>, <i>L. cicera</i>, <i>L. ochrus</i>
Lentil	2008	Global Strategy for the <i>Ex Situ</i> Conservation of Lentil (<i>Lens</i> Miller)
Maize	2007	Global Strategy for the <i>Ex Situ</i> Conservation and Utilisation of Maize Germplasm
Millet	2022	Global Strategy for the Conservation and Use of Genetic Resources of Selected Millets
Oat	2008	Global Strategy for the <i>Ex Situ</i> Conservation of Oats (<i>Avena</i> spp.)
Pea	2023	Global Strategy for the Conservation and Use of Pea Genetic Resources
Peanut	2022	Global Strategy for the Conservation and Use of Peanut Genetic Resources

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Pearl millet	2012	Global Strategy for the <i>Ex Situ</i> Conservation of Pearl Millet and its Wild Relatives
Potato	2006	Global Strategy for the <i>Ex Situ</i> Conservation of Potato
Potato	2022	Global Strategy for the Conservation of Potato
Rice	2010	Global Strategy for the <i>Ex Situ</i> Conservation of Rice Genetic Resources
Sorghum	2007	Strategy for the Global <i>Ex Situ</i> Conservation of Sorghum Genetic Diversity
Sorghum	2022	Global Strategy for the Conservation and Use of Sorghum (<i>Sorghum bicolor</i> (L.) Moench) Genetic Resources
Sunflower	2023	Global Strategy for the Conservation and Use of Sunflower (<i>Helianthus annuus</i>) Genetic Resources
Sweetpotato	2007	Global Strategy for the <i>Ex Situ</i> Conservation of Sweetpotato Genetic Resources
Tea	2019	A Global Strategy for the Conservation and Use of Tea Genetic Resources
Vanilla	2021	Global Strategy for the Conservation and Use of Vanilla Genetic Resources
Vigna	2023	Global Strategy for the Conservation and Use of <i>Vigna</i>
Wheat	2007	Global Strategy for the <i>Ex situ</i> Conservation with Enhanced Access to Wheat, Rye, Triticale Genetic Resources
Yams	2010	Towards a Global Strategy for the Conservation and Use of Yam
Yams	2021	Global Strategy for the Conservation and Use of Yam Genetic Resources

